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1. Synopsis

1.1 Health condition

Parkinson's Disease (PD).

1.2 Study Overview

An observational, cross-sectional, anonymous survey using a modified Delphi process (Jones and Hunter 1995). Participants of three research centres will be asked to rate the importance of 27 questions related to PD. In the first Delphi round held at all sites, there will be the chance to add one question the participant feels is not represented by the 27 questions (identified by Deane et al 2014). The results are then ranked in order of priority score to form the Top 10 Research Priorities for the management of PD. Participants will be asked to give anonymous information including some details to consider confounding factors.

Participants from Oxford will be invited and 50 randomly selected to form a Delphi Panel, who will then review the ratings from the first round with the addition of up to 10 questions identified from the free text inserted priorities. The Delphi panel will rate the importance of all questions and repeat this process until 80% or more agree on the top 10 priorities.

Nominal group technique (NGT) focus groups will be held in UOXF with one group of PwP (with carer if needed) alone and one group of PwP and researchers. The group size will be 10-12 people per group and will follow a structured, moderated approach (Davies et al., 2011). Participants will be shown the results from the simple survey and any additional questions. Members will be asked to rate and rank the priorities independently. After which, each member will share their feedback/results in a "round-robin", they are then invited to rank again independently followed by a moderated discussion between the group to gain consensus (McMillan et al., 2016).

Results from round 1 of the simple survey will be compared to the results from the final Delphi panel round and NGTs to consider how the different consensus methodologies effect the results.

1.3 Inclusion Criteria

Participants of the longitudinal, observational study cohorts, led by the three CENTRE-PD institutions (Discovery, Oxford Parkinson's Disease Centre, University of Oxford [UOXF]; ABC-PD, University of Tübingen, Germany [EKUT]; LuxPARK, University of Luxembourg, Luxembourg [UL]); friends and relatives of participants; members of email lists and cohort outreach groups; all researchers involved in the aforementioned cohort studies (clinicians, nurses, scientists); Allied Health Care Professionals working at/with the aforementioned cohort studies institutes such as: Neurologists, PD nurses, Gerontologists, Physiotherapists, Occupational Therapists, General Practitioners, Speech and Language Therapists.

1.4 Date of first enrolment

1st August 2018 (estimate). Anticipated end July 2020.

1.5 Sample Size

Potential to combine over 2,000 participants from three international sites.

1.6 Recruitment Status

Pending: participants not yet being recruited or enrolled at any site.

1.7 Primary Outcome

To establish the top 10 research priorities of people with PD, friends/family, researchers, clinicians and allied health care professionals.

1.8 Secondary Outcome

To find out how research priorities of clinicians and researchers align with people with Parkinson's. To understand whether there are any differences in priorities across international geographical location or based on confounding factors such as: socioeconomic status and duration of disease. To establish how well research projects being conducted align with the priorities of People with Parkinson's (PwP). To give guidance to form future systematic review questions important to PwP and to guide the dissemination of our cohort research data to the participants. What, if any, differences there are between simple rating prioritisation and Delphi panel prioritisation when establishing consensus.

1.9 Ethics Review

All three centres contacted local research bodies for advice. One centre (EKUT), decided to include the survey as part of a cohort substantial amendment (REC Number 284/2018BO2), and will be linking returned surveys to participant study data if applicable. They may also collect survey responses in the ambulatory clinic during cohort visits. The remainder of the surveys at this site will remain anonymous. The other two sites (UOXF and UL), will keep all survey responses anonymous. Both local REC bodies (Dr Helen Bamby-Porritt, MS IDREC Manager, Research Services, University of Oxford, Wellington Square, Oxford, OX1 2JD, UK) advised that we do not require ethics review for an anonymous survey as this would be considered patient and public involvement (PPI) or service evaluation, rather than research.

1.10 IPD sharing statement

This protocol will be published/registered in its entirety and available to all.

All survey data will be anonymised. One institute will link responses to anonymised clinical cohort data using REDCap, a secure research database. This data will not be available to the other sites as is part of the cohort study data at EKUT.

All email addresses collected for panel inclusion will be stored separately and securely. These will not be shared with partner institutes and will be deleted if the participant is not selected for the panel. All email addresses will be removed once the panel has concluded.

All data collected for this survey will be available in its raw, anonymous form and available upon request. The full ranking of all questions will be available as supplementary material if published or upon request. Any identifiable information will be removed.

2. Abbreviations

CRTG- Clinical Research Trial Governance

EKUT - University of Tübingen

GP – General Practitioners

IDREC – Interdivisional Research Ethics Committee

NGT – Nominal Group Technique

OPDC – Oxford Parkinson's Disease Centre

PD – Parkinson's Disease

PPI – Patient Public Involvement

PSP – Priority Setting Group

PwP – People with Parkinson's

RBD – Rapid Eye Movement Behaviour Disorder

SALT- Speech and Language Therapist

UL – University of Luxembourg

UOXF – University of Oxford

WHO – World Health Organisation

3. Background and Rationale

Parkinson's is a neurodegenerative disorder which can include symptoms of rigidity, tremor, bradykinesia, postural imbalance and cognitive impairment. Depression and Dementia are both

highly prevalent in people with PD. PD prevalence is estimated to be between 35.8 and 12,500 per 100,000 (Cacabelos 2017). A meta-analysis by Pringsheim et al (2014) indicates that PD incidence is rising and with it will come a growing population with considerable emotional stress and economic burden. Worldwide prevalence is variable with one reason being attributed to the variation in survival time across countries and low incidence of medical record keeping in some regions (Muangpaisan et al 2011).

In 2014, the James Lind Alliance and Parkinson's UK collaborated to create a Parkinson's Priority Setting Partnership (PSP). Research has been criticised for being overly influenced by pharmaceutical and medical device companies therefore, PSP groups aim to address the questions about treatments that are of great importance to the patients and participants of trials, friends/family members and clinicians (Crowe et al 2015 and Tallon, Chard and Dieppe 2000). For research to be meaningful, focus needs to be on the effectiveness of treatment options and care provision. This will give greater depth to the evidence-based healthcare approach and will improve recruitment to and participation in clinical trials.

PSP groups identify "treatment uncertainties" which are defined as questions that have not been adequately addressed by research, established through systematic searches of existing research evidence. The findings aim to inform research funding strategies and policies. Deane et al (2014) identified the Top 10 (and top 26) Research Priorities for PD, by asking what PwP, family/friends, clinicians and allied health care professionals involved with management of PD wanted to see addressed by clinical research.

The Discovery cohort is a longitudinal, observational study, assessing PD, "at-risk" of PD, RBD and control participants every 18 months. From this study, a lot of varied data is being collected, helping to understand and target pathological pathways of PD. Throughout the course of Discovery, 1,728 participants have volunteered to take part in the study, 1,309 of whom are still under active follow up (either by telephone or clinic). At a Research Participant Open Day in Oxford, UK, in May 2016, with approximately 150 participants, Assoc. Prof. Dr Michele Hu (Chief Investigator of Discovery cohort) informally introduced the findings from Dean et al (2014) and revisited this concept with those present, asking the participants what they most wanted to get out of their participation in PD research (the results of the informal UOXF survey can be found in the Appendix).

We found our participants selected different priorities than what was ascertained in the PSP group in 2014 and we had many free text responses of priorities that were not listed. Therefore, it was decided appropriate to formally approach the survey. We would like to find out what participants in the cohort most want to be addressed by PD research, how this aligns with what our researchers, scientists, and healthcare professionals deem a priority, and how we can address the questions that are identified.

We also wish to invite allied healthcare professionals working within Parkinson's to participate so we can understand the priorities for health care professionals and clinicians with experience in Parkinson's.

From the top 10 priorities, we will be able to design our future research, systematic reviews, clinical trials and the dissemination of results of our research more effectively, to ensure the needs of our participants are met and that their participation is rewarded in a meaningful way.

Oxford Parkinson's Disease Centre (OPDC), who host the Discovery Cohort through the University of Oxford (UOXF), are collaboratively working with similar patient cohorts at the University of Tübingen, Germany (EKUT) and the University of Luxembourg (UL) through a Horizon2020 project called CENTRE-PD. This will allow for the unique opportunity to assess patient priorities internationally and with a greater number of PwP, clinicians, allied healthcare professionals and friends/families.

By surveying the participants in all three cohorts, as well as clinicians and researchers we will be able to see: a) how research priorities of clinicians and researchers align with our participants and PwP; b) what areas of PD need further research to better support PwP; c) if research priorities differ according to geographical location and other confounding factors; d) how well researchers utilise the patient priorities once identified, consequently, indicating how well our researchers and others address the needs and wants of the participants volunteering in our projects. It may also form guidance on what research is relevant to our participants when we disseminate our results.

Following the establishment of the Top 10 priorities, a thematic search of research projects submitted for ethical approval or, concluded or registered in clinical trial registries and bibliographic databases will be conducted (See Chapter 8.3). A descriptive comparison of the surveyed top three priorities to the actual research conducted in the medical community may allow for recommendation into future research proposals and research projects including systematic reviews of current research.

4. Research Objectives:

1. What are the Top 10 Research Priorities of PwP, friends/families, clinicians and allied health care professionals?
2. How do research priorities of health care professionals and researchers align with people with Parkinson's?
3. Are there any differences in priorities across international geographical locations?
4. Are there differences in priorities based on confounding factors such as socioeconomic status and duration of disease?
5. Is there a correspondence between the Top 10 Research Priorities (patients and caregiver ratings) and the clinical profile of PD patients (EKUT data only)?
6. Alignment of research priorities with research projects by searching of research submitted for ethical approval, registered in clinical trial registries or published in bibliographic databases with the deduced priorities;
7. Guidance to form future systematic review questions important to PwP;
8. What, if any, differences are there between the results of simple rating (round 1) prioritisation, Delphi panel prioritisation and NGT with and without healthcare professionals?

5. Participants

5.1 Eligible Participants

All participants of the PD research cohorts associated with CENTRE-PD (UOXF, EKUT and UL) will be invited to complete the survey and are invited to share the survey with their friends and family. All members of email lists related to the cohorts, study centres or CENTRE-PD will be invited (includes participants, people interested in PD, students, health care professionals, researchers and scientists, etc.).

We will invite health care professionals working within Parkinson's to participate. The following health care professionals have been identified: Neurologists, Neurosurgeons, Gerontologists, PD Nurses, Speech and Language Therapists (SALT), Physiotherapists, Researchers (doctors, nurses, academics, laboratory staff), GPs, ward staff (Neuro and Gerontology). Each site will contact the clinical lead/matron/team leader of their local teams to ask them to distribute the electronic survey amongst their staff. An email will be sent to local GP practices with the link to the electronic survey asking it to be distributed to the GPs at each site.

There is no specific inclusion or exclusion criteria as this is a feedback survey only that participants are requested to complete the survey only once.

5.2 Blinding and Allocation

All participants will be invited to complete the same survey and have the option to give demographic information. There is no blinding or allocation to an intervention or different type of survey.

Only UOXF will be able to participate in the Delphi panel and NGTs due to difficulties around consent, travel restrictions and sharing contact information internationally.

Delphi panel - If more than 50 participants from Oxford leave contact details to be included in the Delphi panel, a random sequence generator, stratified by PwP and health care professional will be used to randomly select 50 people at a rate of 1:1 (25 PwP, 25 others). A generous 50 people will make up the panel to control for drop outs between Delphi rounds. So long as at least 20 people completing the final priority making there should be good significance in the results.

NGT – For the mixed NGT, members of the OPDC research team and associate healthcare professionals, who are not in the Delphi panel but have completed the simple survey, will be invited to participate in the half-day meeting. The remainder of NGT will be PwP who have completed the survey and if needed, their carer. PwP will be invited from a local research interested list to take part in the NGT when invited to do the simple survey. 15-16 PwP and 5-6 researchers who volunteer their time will be randomly selected and invited to the John Radcliffe Hospital for the 4-hour NGT.

5.3 Recruitment

The voluntary nature of the survey will be explained as so in the instructions:

“Responses to this survey are completely voluntary and there is no obligation for you to take part.”

Participants from the research cohorts: Discovery, ABC PD, LuxPARK, will be sent the Rating Pack (supplementary material) by post and/or email. For those whom we have an email address for, an electronic link to the survey (on REDCap or Qualtrics dependent on site) will be sent with an electronic copy of the Rating Pack. For those who receive a postal pack, a freepost envelope will be included so no cost to the participant will be incurred.

A link to an electronic version of the Rating Pack will also be included in the postal pack. Contact details will be provided should patients wish to contact the local researcher to ask for an electronic link to be sent by email or for guidance on navigating the postal/electronic versions of the form. The electronic version of the survey will be available on a REDCap database in EKUT and UL, and on Qualtrics in UOXF (this will reduce costs at UOXF site). All forms returned by post, will be manually inputted into the local database by the research team. Participants can choose to either return their rating sheet by post or to directly input the data online, which ever they feel more comfortable doing.

The participants may wish to pass the survey on to family and friends, and as we would like to collect data from all people who experience PD the following has been included on the information sheet:

“If you have any family members or friends that you think may be interested in participating, please share this with them. They can contact local researcher for a postal form or complete the form electronically using the link above.”

This will help to increase our survey responses from this group of people as the majority of our participants are PwP. For members of the cohorts whom we know live with a family/friend we may distribute two rating sheets to give them the opportunity to complete should they wish to.

To get a good response from allied health care professionals, each site will contact managers, clinical leads, GPs, sisters or matrons of the identified clinical areas of interest and ask them to kindly distribute the electronic Rating Pack (by email) to their staff for voluntary completion.

To ensure that all persons who receive the survey or who are informed of the survey through family members only complete the survey once (by post or online), the following has been included:

“Please only complete this survey ONCE.”

To allow time for people to receive postal packs and ensure that an adequate amount of time has been given for the return of postal forms, and for further analyses, we will keep the databases (for data entry or direct input) open for 24 months from the date the first participant is contacted at the first site.

EKUT, who have included the survey in a recent cohort Substantial Amendment will also be able to collect data during research clinics in the ambulatory/outpatient area. Data will be collected either on paper CRF or on a tablet form directly into REDCap with a clinician if the participant has given valid informed consent.

Recruitment to the Delphi panel in UOXF is through the simple survey consent form. Participants are explained what the Delphi panel will entail (several more rounds of simple survey) and what their email addresses will be used for. They are invited to leave their email address underneath a consent box for the Delphi panel if they agree, or to move straight on to the simple survey without enrolling for the panel randomisation. Please see the Supplementary Material (Rating Pack) for more information.

For the mixed NGT, members of the OPDC research team and associate healthcare professionals, who are not in the Delphi panel but have completed the simple survey, will be invited to participate in the half-day meeting. The remainder of NGT will be PwP who have completed the survey and if needed, their carer.

PwP will be invited from a local research interested list to take part in the NGT when invited to do the simple survey. 15-16 PwP and 5-6 researchers who volunteer their time will be randomly selected and invited to the John Radcliffe Hospital for the 4-hour NGT.

5.5 Consent

Recent changes to general data protection regulations (GDPR 2018) mean that simply returning the survey as a form of implied consent is problematic. The associated guidance on affirmative consent, state the affirmative act leaves ambiguity to the further use of data beyond what is obvious and necessary. Therefore, we will include a confirmation of their willingness to participate in the pooled meta-analyses and for their consent to process or share their anonymous or confidential information as per the planned purposes described on the consent page. Participants in UOXF will also have a consent page related to the Delphi Panel. The consent form will be an anonymous tick form, unless the participant leaves an email address for the random selection to the panel. In this instance, the email address will be removed from the survey responses for data pooling. Postal forms returned without consent will be destroyed and no data used. Any postal forms returned with email addresses but which do not have ticked consent to the Delphi panel, will be contacted once to confirm consent. If there is no response the email address will be removed.

On the electronic version of the survey, branching logic will be used which will inhibit participants from continuing if they do not consent to the “Survey Consent” statements. They may continue without consenting to “Delphi Consent”. On the “Delphi Consent” electronic form, the option to add an email address will only appear if all items have been consented to. This is clearly explained to participants on both consent forms. If postal forms are returned without consent but survey data filled in, the survey data will not be entered into the database. Likewise, if an email address is supplied without sufficient consent it will not be added to the database.

The consent form can be found in Supplementary Material.

5.6 Participant Confidentiality

EKUT plan to also collect the cohort study pseudonym where applicable; where the study ID is not collected the rating will remain completely anonymous. By collecting the study ID, they will be able to match the survey response to their clinical research data. They can then comment whether responses to the survey are influenced by PD symptoms alone or anticipation of degeneration. Only people who include their participant ID will be matched to their clinical research data which is also anonymised. The data collected for the survey will be completely anonymous with no reference to individual clinical or research data. Their cohort study data will not be shared with staff outside of EKUT. However, data of the Top 10 Research Priorities will be transferred to UOXF and UL if the patients had agreed to the transfer of the anonymised data.

UOXF and UL will collect all rating anonymously with no link to study data. All forms can be returned anonymously however; UOXF participants may leave email details if they wish to be selected for the Delphi panel. Email addresses will not be shared with any institutes outside of University of Oxford and the email addresses will be removed from the raw data and stored separately and securely. Those who are not selected for the panel will have their email addresses removed and once the panel has concluded, all email addresses will be deleted from the system. Any participant identifiable information will not be uploaded on to the database and will be censored from any analyses.

6. Study Procedures

6.1 Overview of Study Design

An anonymous survey will be distributed to eligible participants by post and/or email. Participants will be invited to give anonymous information including some details to consider confounding factors in secondary analyses (responder type, gender, ethnicity, years of education completed, household income and participation in research). PwP will also be asked: current age, age of onset (if applicable), and living arrangements so that we may comment on whether duration of disease or independence status change the priorities. In the first round of surveys, participants will be asked to rate each priority on how important it is to them using a simple rating scale of 1-9. Then the medians and inter-quartile ranges will be calculated and the priorities will then be ranked in order of importance. The ranked order of all three sites will be the overall defined “Top 10 Priorities for the Management of PD”.

UOXF participants will then have subsequent rounds. A Delphi panel, who are given the list of priorities in the order of ranking from Round 1. The panel will rate each question again until a substantial majority of the panel agree that the Top 10 is correct. There will be no further adding of questions in the following rounds. An NGT of all PwP (target population) and an NGT with PwP and healthcare professionals (mixed stakeholders) will also be conducted. This will allow comparison of how NGT with “experts” in compared to PwP alone, effects the final ranking/consensus methodology.

6.2 Selecting the Survey Questions

In the 2014 PSP group, 94 questions were created as potentially unanswered uncertainties, identified by systematic searching of medical research and sent out to members of Parkinson's UK for ranking. From this survey the top 26 priorities were formed following which a focus group was held to determine the top 10. It was decided that 94 questions would be too time consuming and reduce responses from our participants and that the top 26 would be sufficient at this time. Once the results of our survey have been ascertained, we may be able to give advice on future PSP groups for PD as hopefully, some of the top 26 questions will have been answered in recent years (although this is not definite).

During the informal survey of the OPDC participants in May 2016, 6.16% of patients wrote in free text (not requested) that they also would like to see questions pertaining to speech addressed (results of informal survey in Appendix I). Of the original 94 questions created by the PSP group, one was related to speech in PD. Ms Francesca Bowring contacted the original PSP group to get the full ranking of all 94 questions, the question “*What speech therapy techniques are helpful for communication problems in people with Parkinson's?*” was ranked 44 out of 94. As this was of particular interest to some of our research participants, we decided to include this question in our survey.

During round one of the survey, a free text element option, allowing participants to write down a priority they feel has been missed, is included. Any returned free text will be organised into themed categories, and any repetition in theme will be turned in to an appropriate research question/priority. No more than 10 additional questions will be created and then distributed to the Delphi panel so these may be included in the consensus prioritisation.

Therefore, the first round of the survey will include the top 26 from the original 94 questions, with the addition of the ability to write a free text answer (creating a priority they feel is not addressed by the survey) and a question pertaining to speech, a total of 28 questions. The panel rounds will include the original 27 questions plus the 10 thematic questions (made from the free-text responses), totalling 37 questions to be rated.

6.3 Variable Data Identification

Parkinson's UK were contacted for permission to adapt literature created during the first survey and PSP group and a Rating Pack (see supplementary material) has been created. The information we will be collecting for all participants is limited to: participant type (PwP, clinician etc.), current age, gender, ethnic background, and previous participation in research. For PwP, we will also collect: age at diagnosis, living arrangements, highest education level and whether they live above/below the local poverty line. These confounders are optional and participants may select “*Prefer not to say*” if they choose so. Collecting these variables will allow us to do a regression analysis for these various confounders and give comment on the generalisability of the results. These analyses will support/reject the hypotheses that we will get:

- i) A greater response from PwP recently diagnosed with PD. By the collection of ages, we can identify trends in not only rate of response but also whether there are observed differences in the priorities of newly diagnosed versus more advanced PD.
- ii) The majority of responders will live at home independently/we expect to see far fewer responses from those in Nursing Homes or Residential Homes.
- iii) It was identified that there had been a very small amount of replies from ethnic minorities in the previous PSP group (Deane et al. 2014) so, information on participant ethnic background remains a confounder of interest. We expect the majority of our responses will be white background as this reflects the population of the cohorts (approximately 98% white ethnicity in Discovery).
- iv) Whether people from a low-income household are more likely to prioritise questions related to being able to return to work opposed to longevity/quality of life. Whether there are differences in priorities based on financial stability.

- v) The expectation that the majority of our responders will be individuals who have completed higher education and participated in research (as a participant or researcher).

Luxembourg and Tübingen will not collect information relating to specific ethnicity. The Luxembourgish society is very heterogeneous in ethnicity and thus finding the correct terminology to ask for this classification was difficult. Therefore, they will include the following question: "Do you have the nationality of the country you live in? Yes/No/Prefer not to say". In England, Ms Francesca Bowring adapted ethnic groups identified from the Census (The Office for National Statistics 2011).

The poverty line was ascertained in each country. In the UK, relative poverty from the Department for Work and Pensions (2018) before housing costs is approximately £15,392 per year (calculated as 60% of the population median income). In Luxembourg the median disposable income per household 2015 was 4514€ per month (STATEC 2017). The poverty line is approximately 2708€ (calculated as 60% of the population median income). In EKUT, the number of subjects living in the household and the poverty line for one-person (969 €) and family household (2035 €) as well as the intermediate category (between 969 € and 2035 €) will be assessed.

In regards to the educational level, there will be difficulty distinguishing the lower levels (1-4) in Germany, therefore, they will ask participants what their highest qualification is. UOXF will use the educational levels defined by Gov.UK (date unknown). The European guidance on Education Level can be found at: <https://ec.europa.eu/ploteus/en/content/descriptors-page>.

6.4 Participant Timeline

Participants from UL will be invited to complete the one-time survey anonymously and with no obligation to take part. EKUT participants will be invited to complete anonymously either as part of the cohort research clinic or by electronic link anonymously.

Some participants from Oxford will be selected as the Delphi panel and will supply an email address to complete the rating again, until consensus is reached. The first Delphi round will be open for six months; subsequent rounds will be open to responses for 4 weeks per round.

Participants for the NGT will be invited to a half-day meeting at the John Radcliffe Hospital, Oxford. After this event there is no further obligation for the participant. Participants can have their travel costs reimbursed but will not receive any other benefit from participating.

The remainder of UOXF participants will only need to complete the survey once anonymously.

Participants from all three sites can continue on any other clinical trials, studies or with medical care that they are receiving. There will be no changes to lifestyle or care given.

Participants are not obliged to finish the survey and incomplete surveys on the electronic databases will be deleted after the database closes if they have not been completed the rating as described in section 9.3.

6.5 Definition of End of Study

The first Delphi round will be open for six months. Subsequent Delphi rounds will be open for data collection for 4 weeks per round. The database will remain open and data can be entered for 24 months from project start in case of future analyses with greater number of participants.

6.6 Study Expenses and Benefits

Benefits of participating are limited to the potential to shape future research that is aimed at meeting the needs of those affected by PD. It will also aim to make communication and dissemination of research results to those who participate more relatable and relevant. Contact details will be available for the local researcher for participants to get guidance and support if needed.

There is no compensation to be given for participation. Only the costs of returning the Rating Pack will be covered, there is no other financial incentive or burden for participants.

6.7 Translation of the Survey Questions

The survey and rating pack were translated at each site using the World Health Organisation (WHO) Process of translation and adaption of instruments whereby, it is first translated in to the needed language, then back translated or, retranslated back to English by another person.

7. Safety

7.1 Safety and Monitoring

Contact details to local team members are available to give participants support should they need it. No risk has been identified for completing this survey and participants will be given links to the previous publications and local researchers should they have concerns or want to find out more information.

7.2 Adverse Events/Serious Adverse Events

There are no adverse events or serious adverse events associated with the rating survey. We will not collect data on any SAE occurred during the recruitment period. All participants will be contacted by postal or electronic mail and have the option to complete the survey in their own time.

7.3 Ethical Considerations

Central University Research Ethics Committee (CUREC) were contacted for advice for the UOXF. EKUT submitted the survey as an amendment to their cohort study. UL received advice from local ethics. PwP may fall into vulnerable participant category but the optional nature of the survey is explained and contact details should the participant wish to contact the local researcher will be present. There is no harm likely to occur as a result of completing this survey.

9. Prioritisation and Analyses

8.1 Prioritisation – establishing the Top 10

A modified Delphi process will be used where in round one, participants at all three sites will be invited to rate the importance of each question on a scale of 1 to 9, with 1 being not at all important and 9 being very important. The participants may also add one question they feel is not represented by the original JLA survey and rate its importance. All free-text questions will be summarised and grouped according to its theme. No more than 10 additional questions from the free text will be included therefore, only the most popular free text responses will be included in subsequent Delphi rounds if more than 10 are identified.

The median and interquartile range will be calculated for every question and then placed in order of score to form the prioritised list in ranking from most important to least important. This list will be the final prioritisation from EKUT and UL and will indicate the Top 10 Priorities for all three sites using a simple survey (round 1).

Subsequent Delphi rounds at UOXF will be initialised once the first ranking list is created. The results will be shared with the randomly selected Delphi panel who are asked to rate the importance of all the questions from the first round and the additional questions that were formed by the free text responses. They may keep their original rating or change the ratings completely. Again, the median and interquartile ranges are formed and the top 10 priorities will be established.

If there is less than 80% consensus on the top 10, that is, the questions with the top 10 highest medians have been rated as highly important (7-9) by fewer than 80% of the Delphi panel, the round will be repeated until there is agreement. There will be as many rounds as needed to establish the final top 10. A feedback survey will be sent out with the final results which is optional for the panel to complete.

After the simple survey, two separate NGT meetings will be held over half-day time periods; one with both healthcare professionals and PwP and, another with only PwP (and carer if needed). In both NGTs, participants will first go through the results of the simple survey silently and independently. Making notes and prioritising the questions using the same ranking scale as before. Following this, a round-robin will be conducted where each person will be allowed to give one piece of feedback per turn. Following this another independent rating session. They will also be asked to choose the priority most important to them for open discussion. A moderated discussion will commence and once at least 80% of the group agree on the final top 10 the session will end. A feedback survey will be given to the participants which is optional for them to complete. An independent observer will make notes during the meetings.

By doing this, we will be able to comment on the overall consensus of the consortium based on the original Deane et al questions and the difference (if any) in the prioritisation following the addition of free text options created by the first Delphi round. This will also allow us to comment on the difference between the four consensus methods, simple prioritisation (round 1 only), the modified Delphi process, NGT with mixed stakeholders and the NGT with only the target population.

8.2 Statistical Analyses

The Primary Outcome analysis will include the final prioritisation after the first Delphi panel rating and will form the “Top 10 Research Priorities in PD”. The median and interquartile ranges for every question will be presented and ranked in order of median score. The results from the Delphi panel and NGTs at UOXF will also be described and compared.

The secondary outcomes analyses that will be presented are as follows:

- i) The difference (if any) between two sub groups: PwP and family/friends verses carers and healthcare professionals and will be “Alignment of research priorities with PwP and friends/family of PwP. The Top 10 for each subgroup will be identified then compared with one another for discussion. This will be from the round 1 results as there may be an uneven number of PwP and clinicians in the successive Delphi panel rounds and will include all three sites.
- ii) An analysis will be done based on round 1 results comparing the top 10 by geographical location, i.e. UOXF vs EKUT vs UL.
- iii) Regression analyses by the various confounders collected in round 1 (e.g. whether age, disease duration, socioeconomic etc.) have an effect on priorities.

8.3 Summative Text Analyses

Other secondary outcomes will be assessed through descriptive text. The first will assess the alignment of research projects with the final Top 3 priorities. This will be done by searching of research submitted for ethical approval, registered in clinical trial registries or published in bibliographic databases.

The following places have been identified for searching: The Cochrane Movement Disorder Specialised Register; The Cochrane Library; The Cochrane Controlled Trials Register (Wiley Online); MEDLINE (Ovid); PubMed; EMBASE(Ovid); CINAHL; ISI Web of Science: Science Citation Index Expanded; ISI Web of Science: Conference Proceedings Citation Index, AMED, WHO International Clinical Trials Registry Platform; UK Clinical Trials Gateway; ClinicalTrials.gov; DISSABS (DISSertation ABSTRACTs); Conference Papers Index (ProQuest); Index to Theses; ProQuest dissertations and theses databases; Electronic Theses Online Service (ETHOS)

The search terms will be created using the priority question and key PD terms such as:

- Parkinson* OR PD OR MeSH descriptor [Parkinson*] explode all trees.

Following this systematic search and comparison of current research to the priorities, we will be able to give guidance on areas that need further research, either by clinical trials or systematic reviews. In addition, it will help guide the research teams at all sites about what information to disseminate to the participants in their local cohorts.

The final descriptive summary will be an assessment of the benefit of using a Delphi panel process to establish consensus. A comparison of the results from UOXF during round 1 and the final Delphi round will be described with recommendations on future consensus methods if applicable.

10. Data Management

9.1 Data Storage

EKUT and UL will collect and store their survey responses on REDCap which is a confidential clinical research database with secure access. The UOXF has an account with Qualtrics which is an online survey tool that is currently used by 1,700 universities and users are able to easily design, distribute, analyse, and report on survey data confidentially. Both online databases can be exported to an Excel format. All results from round one will be pooled on one Excel spreadsheet and analysed accordingly. To ensure all sites collect the same data, the field headers will be the same for all three sites to enable an easy merge process. Data will be stored on a University of Oxford computer with password security and encryption.

Any confidential data will remain with the home institute and will not be shared with the international partners. Only anonymous data from the survey responses will be shared and pooled to form the analyses. Any confidential information and contact details supplied to the sites will be removed from the database and stored separately and securely. Once final priorities have been established in the Delphi panel, all email and personal identifiable information will be deleted. Notes will be taken during the NGT by an independent observer. These notes will be kept and used to help with descriptive analysis.

Local sites will keep the anonymous survey data and notes for 10 years in case of data audit.

9.2 Data Availability

Raw anonymous data can be made available to researchers on request following publication. This data will be anonymous and just inform the reader of the data used to calculate the priorities.

9.3 Missing Data and Validation

Completed postal surveys will be inputted directly on to the online database by the local researcher. Postal forms returned without consent will be destroyed and no data used. Any postal forms returned with email addresses but which do not have ticked consent to the Delphi panel, will be contacted once to confirm consent. If there is no response the email address will be removed.

Surveys partially completed will be assessed for inclusion as follows: if 30% or more of the questions for rating are missed, the form will be omitted from the database; if demographic information is missing the rating will be included and “prefer not to say” boxes will be checked; if responder type is missing, the survey will not be inputted.

The online database will use branching logic and compulsory field validation to ensure all questions which are compulsory are answered and that participants are not able to progress with the survey without giving valid consent. If a participant does not give consent to one of the survey consent questions online, the survey will skip to the following message:

Thank you for visiting the Survey today. As you have not given consent to one or more of the domains you will not be able to continue with the survey. If you think this is an error, please click the back arrow at the bottom of the page and then read the statements carefully - make sure you check the boxes if appropriate.

The participant may either go back to the consent screen (in case one is missed by mistake) or be able to select to end the survey from this point. This will skip them to the end of the survey where Ms Francesca Bowring’s contact details and a brief thank you message is displayed.

The online database will only present the question’s for PwP if the “Person with Parkinson’s” option is selected in the participant type question (which is a mandatory question). All participants will be invited to complete demographic information which may be left blank by selecting the option “Prefer not to say”.

The following webpage will present all of the questions to be rated, each with a sliding scale from 1 - 9. All scales start automatically at 1, but if the participant does not click on the scale to select the answer 1, the survey will assume they have missed the question and will not let them progress to the next page. This is to prevent a question being missed and scored as 1 incorrectly.

They may also add a question they feel has been missed and rank this at the bottom of this webpage. Finally, before they continue, they are asked to check and validate their answers as so:

*Please now check you are happy with your answers.
If you have finished, click next to submit your answers.*

Once they are finished they may click next which will end the survey. If on the web version of the survey they close the window before completion this will be called a partial response. Partial responses will be kept open to data entry for 1 week should the participant go back to the survey in their web browser to complete at a later date. After this date, the participant will need to start a new survey form. Partial responses will be recorded on to the database automatically and will then be assessed as per the postal forms and deleted/anonymised as appropriate.

10. Study Limitations

The majority of our PwP responders will be research participants. This could lead to poor generalisability as it is expected that research participants are more likely to be middle-class, higher educated individuals. It is more likely that those without literacy issues would respond. Parkinson’s is also very heterogenous in its presentation therefore achieving consensus could be challenging. We may also find that people with

more severe PD, or patients with severe co-morbidities would be less likely to respond which could increase difficulties in generalising the data to the PD population as a whole. As the previous PSP group found it difficult to get responses from black and minority groups we are expecting a similar trend.

11. Study Monitoring and Oversight

Who will be responsible for day-to-day supervision of the study?
Ms Francesca Bowring, Project Manager/Research Nurse
Give information about frequency of meetings that will be held to discuss progress/problems. Who will be present at the meetings?
Teleconferences will be held between the main author and co-authors every three months. Ms Francesca Bowring will co-ordinate communication to Ms Patricia Sulzer and Ms Anne-Marie Hanff through email correspondence and telephone conferences needed to resolve any issues between the quarterly calls.

12. Ethical and Regulatory Considerations

12.1 Declaration of Helsinki

The Investigator will ensure that this study is conducted in accordance with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki.

12.2 Approvals

The protocol, informed consent form, and participant information sheet will be submitted to the Medical Sciences IDREC for written approval.

The Investigator will submit and, where necessary, obtain approval from the Sponsor and the above parties for all amendments to the original approved documents.

12.3 Annual Progress Report

The main author shall submit an Annual Progress Report to the Medical Sciences Interdivisional Research Ethics Committee (MS IDREC) with a copy to Clinical Trials Research Governance.

13. Insurance Statement

The University has a specialist insurance policy in place which would operate in the event of any participant suffering harm as a result of their involvement in the research (Newline Underwriting Management Ltd, at Lloyd's of London). For all PwW of the ABC-PD study a clinical trial insurance will cover any harm based on the study participation (Number of insurance police: 57 010311 03013; Insurance Period: 15.08.2018 until 31.12.2020; Amount of damage compensation: 500,000.00€ per participant, Maximum limit of indemnity is 5,000,000.00€ (for all 209 participants). No travel accident insurance will be offered.

14. Dissemination

We hope to publish the results from our survey in to an international journal. This protocol will be registered on zenodo.com to allow for full transparency of the research methods used and for peer review.

15. References

- Cacabelos R, 2017, Parkinson's Disease: From Pathogenesis to Pharmacogenomics, *Int J Mol Sci.* 2017 Mar; 18(3): 551. Published online 2017 Mar 4. doi: 10.3390/ijms18030551
- Crowe S, Fenton M, Hall M, Cowan K, and Chalmers I, 2015, Patients', clinicians' and the research communities' priorities for treatment research: there is an important mismatch, *Research Involvement and Engagement* 2015;1:2, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40900-015-0003-x>
- Davies, S., P. S. Romano, E. M. Schmidt, E. Schultz, J. J. Geppert, and K. M. McDonald, 2011, Assessment of a Novel Hybrid Delphi and Nominal Groups Technique to Evaluate Quality Indicators: *Health Serv Res*, v. 46, p. 2005-18.
- Deane KHO, Flaherty H, Daley DJ, et al. Priority setting partnership to identify the top 10 research priorities for the management of Parkinson's disease. *BMJ Open* 2014;4:e006434. doi:10.1136/bmjopen-2014-006434
- Department of Work and Pensions, 2018, Households Below Average Income: An analysis of the UK income distribution: 1994/95-2016/17, available at: https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/691917/households-below-average-income-1994-1995-2016-2017.pdf#page=2 [accessed on 30/May/2018]
- GOV.UK, (date unknown), What qualification levels mean, available at: <https://www.gov.uk/what-different-qualification-levels-mean/list-of-qualification-levels>
- GDPR, 2017, Consultation: GDPR consent guidance, available at: <https://ico.org.uk/media/about-the-ico/consultations/2013551/draft-gdpr-consent-guidance-for-consultation-201703.pdf>
- Jones J and Hunter D, 1995, Qualitative Research: Consensus methods for medical and health services research *BMJ* 1995; 311 :376, available at: <https://www.bmj.com/content/311/7001/376>
- McMillan, S. S., M. King, and M. P. Tully, 2016, How to use the nominal group and Delphi techniques, *Int J Clin Pharm*, v. 38, p. 655-62.
- Muangpaisan W, Mathews A, Hori H, Seidel D, 2011, A Systematic Review of the Worldwide Prevalence and Incidence of Parkinson's Disease, *J Med Assoc Thai* 2011; 94 (6): 749-55 Full text. e-Journal: <http://www.mat.or.th/journal>
- The Office for National Statistics, 2011, Census, available at: <https://www.ons.gov.uk/census>
- Pringsheim T, Jette N, Frolkis A, Steeves TD, 2014, The prevalence of Parkinson's disease: a systematic review and meta-analysis, *Mov Disord.* 2014 Nov;29(13):1583-90. doi: 10.1002/mds.25945. Epub 2014 Jun 28.
- Tallon D, Chard J and Dieppe P, 2000, Relation between agendas of the research community and the research consumer, *The Lancet*, Volume 355, No. 9220, p2037–2040, 10 June 2000, DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(00\)02351-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(00)02351-5)

16. Declarations and Signatures of Researchers

- I/We, the researcher(s) agree:
- To start this research study only after obtaining approval from MS IDREC/CUREC;
- To carry out this research study only if funding is adequate to enable it to be carried out according to good research practice and in an ethical manner;
- That it is the responsibility of the Principal Investigator to ensure that all researchers working on this project are qualified and either experienced, or have received appropriate ethical training, to conduct the research described;
- To provide additional information as requested by MS IDREC/CUREC before approval is secured and as research progresses;
- To maintain the confidentiality of all data collected from or about study participants;
- To notify CTRG and MS IDREC in writing immediately of any proposed change which would increase the risks that any participant is exposed to and await approval before proceeding with the proposed change;
- To notify CTRG and MS IDREC if the principal researcher on the study changes and supply the name of the successor;
- To notify CTRG and MS IDREC in writing within seven days if any serious *adverse event* occurs in the course of research;
- To use data collected only for the study for which approval has been given;
- To grant access to data only to authorised persons; and
- To maintain security procedures for the protection of personal data, including (but not restricted to): removal of identifying information from data collection forms and computer files, storage of linkage codes in a locked cabinet and password control for access to identified data on computer files.

Principal Investigator (Name)	Assoc. Prof. Dr. Michele Hu
Principal Investigator (Signature)	
Researcher (Name)	Ms Francesca Bowring
Researcher (Signature)	

17. Acceptance by Head of Department/Faculty

*or other senior member of the department if the Principal Investigator is the head of department.

Example nominees include Deputy Head of Department, or, for student projects, Director of Graduate Studies.

- I have read the research application named above.
- On the basis of the information available to me, I judge the Principal Investigator/Supervisor and student researcher (if applicable) to be aware of their ethical responsibilities in regard to this research.
- I am satisfied that the proposed project has been subject to appropriate peer review and is likely to contribute to existing knowledge and/or to the education and training of the researcher(s) and that it is in the public interest.

Head of Department (Name)	Professor Irene Tracy
Head of Department (Signature)	
Date	

18. Amendment History

Amendment No.	Protocol Version No.	Date issued	Author(s) of changes	Details of Changes made
1	2.0	06/Nov/2018	Ms Francesca Bowring	Clarifications for details from EKUT and UL. Addition of two NGTs at UOXF to allow comparison of the different consensus methodologies - simple survey, modified Delphi and Nominal Group Technique. Clarification to handling partially completed postal surveys.

19. Appendix

The Top 10 Questions identified in the 2014 PSP group:

Uncertainty	PwP Score	Carer Score	F&F Score	HSCP Score	Total	Interim rank	A-Z ID
What treatments are helpful in reducing tremor in people with Parkinson's?	93	83	92	91	359	1	T
What treatments are helpful for reducing balance problems and falls in people with Parkinson's?	92	93	80	94	359	1	E
Is it possible to identify different types of Parkinson's, eg, tremor dominant? And can we tailor treatments best according to these different types?	88	88	89	88	353	3	U
What treatments would ensure the medications were equally effective each day (prevented/managed wearing off, variability, on/off states) in people with Parkinson's?	89	94	88	81	352	4	H
Would the monitoring of dopamine levels in the body (eg, with blood tests) be helpful in determining medication timing and amount (dose)?	91	89	86	86	352	4	L
What is helpful for improving the quality of sleep in people with Parkinson's?	94	79.5	93	84	350.5	6	G
What best treats mild cognitive problems such as memory loss, lack of concentration, indecision and slowed thinking in people with Parkinson's?	87	91	77	89.5	344.5	7	D
What treatments are helpful in reducing urinary problems (urgency, irritable bladder, incontinence) in people with Parkinson's?	90	77	94	79	340	8	I
What drug treatments are best for the different stages of Parkinson's?	83	87	87	77.5	334.5	9	X
What approaches are helpful for reducing stress and anxiety in people with Parkinson's?	75	77	82	92	326	10	M
What treatments are helpful for reducing dyskinesias (involuntary movements, which are a side effect of some medications) in people with Parkinson's?	80	90	73.5	77.5	321	11	J
What best treats dementia in people with Parkinson's?	56	92	75	93	316	12	Z
What interventions are effective for reducing or managing unexplained fatigue in people with Parkinson's?	78	65	85	85	313	13	Y
What best helps prevent or reduce freezing (of gait and in general) in people with Parkinson's?	79	71.5	76	82	308.5	14	O
What treatments are helpful for swallowing problems (dysphagia) in people with Parkinson's?	66	74.5	81	80	301.5	15	C
What is the best method of monitoring a person with Parkinson's response to treatments?	81	52.5	83.5	83	300	16	F
What training, techniques or aids are needed for hospital staff, to make sure patients with Parkinson's get their medications correctly and on time?	53	86	64.5	89.5	293	17	W
What treatments are helpful in reducing bowel problems (constipation, incontinence) in people with Parkinson's?	77	85	90	40	292	18	K
What is the best type and dose of exercise (physiotherapy) for improving muscle strength, flexibility, fitness, balance and function in people with Parkinson's?	84	68	64.5	67.5	284	19	Q
Can medications be developed to allow fewer doses per day for people with Parkinson's? (For example combinations of medications in one pill, slow release pills)	73	84	56	69	282	20	S
What helps improve the dexterity (fine motor skills or coordination of small muscle movements) of people with Parkinson's so they can do up buttons, use computers, phones, remote controls etc?	85	59.5	73.5	54.5	272.5	21	A
What treatments are effective in reducing hallucinations (including vivid dreams) in people with Parkinson's?	52	79.5	71.5	61	264	22	P
What is the best treatment for stiffness (rigidity) in people with Parkinson's?	86	67	63	46	262	23	B
At which stage of Parkinson's is deep brain stimulation (a surgical treatment that involves implanting a 'brain pacemaker' that sends signals to specific parts of the brain) most helpful?	69	59.5	91	42	261.5	24	N
What training to improve knowledge and skills do informal carers (family and friends) need in order to best care for people with Parkinson's?	42	82	70	63.5	257.5	25	V
What is the best treatment for pain in people with Parkinson's?	82	54	60.5	57.5	254	26	R

F&F, family and friends; HSCP, health and social care professionals; PwP, people with Parkinson's.

The Top 10 at the OPDC Open Day 2016:

1	Finding a cure for Parkinson's
2	What is the best type and dose of exercise (physiotherapy) for improving muscle strength, flexibility, fitness, balance and function in people with Parkinson's?
3	What helps improve the dexterity (fine motor skills or coordination of small muscle movements) of people with Parkinson's so they can do up buttons, use computers, phones, remote controls etc.? What treatments are effective in reducing hallucinations (including vivid dreams) in people with Parkinson's?
4	What is helpful for improving the quality of sleep in people with Parkinson's?
5	What best treats mild cognitive problems such as memory loss, lack of concentration, indecision and slowed thinking in people with Parkinson's?
6	What approaches are helpful for reducing stress and anxiety in people with Parkinson's?
7	Is it possible to identify different types of Parkinson's, e.g., tremor dominant? And can we tailor treatments best according to these different types?
7	What is the best treatment for stiffness (rigidity) in people with Parkinson's?
8	What drug treatments are best for the different stages of Parkinson's?
9	What interventions are effective for reducing or managing unexplained fatigue in people with Parkinson's?
10	What treatments are helpful for reducing balance problems and falls in people with Parkinson's?
10	Can medications be developed to allow fewer doses per day for people with Parkinson's? (For example, combinations of medications in one pill, slow release pills)